

TDCC-LSH

Life Sciences & Health

**Strengthening the Dutch data driven
health & life sciences field**

TDCC-LSH facts and figures September 2022- August 2024

Colophon

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Authors:

- Celia van Gelder (Health-RI), Network Manager TDCC LSH
- Kimberley Zwiers (Health-RI), Community Coordinator Life Sciences TDCC LSH
- Fieke Schoots (Health-RI), Community Coordinator Health TDCC LSH
- Ruben Kok (Health-RI), Chair Programme Board TDCC LSH

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Contact information TDCC-LSH

- TDCC website: <https://tdcc.nl/>
- Email: lsh@tdcc.nl

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Strengthening the Dutch data driven health & life sciences field

TDCC-LSH facts and figures September 2022- August 2024

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Executive Summary

As part of the implementation programme for the digitisation of scientific research in the Netherlands, NWO has provided funding for the next 10 years to support the formation of three national-level Thematic Digital Competence Centres (TDCC) with complementary network activities and projects to tackle domain specific challenges in data driven science.

The Thematic Digital Competence Centre for Life Sciences and Health (TDCC-LSH), that started in September 2022, offers a programme aimed at strengthening and harmonizing the digital practices among stakeholders in the broad Dutch research domains of life sciences and biomedical/health sciences. This document shows the progress for TDCC-LSH, for the period September 2022 – August 2024.

The TDCC-LSH network builds on the extensive national network in data-driven life sciences and health built around the Dutch Techcentre for Life sciences (DTL) and Health-RI. The TDCC-LSH Roadmap, which was formulated after extensive consultation among LSH stakeholders, guides the TDCC-LSH activities. TDCC-LSH has three main ambitions to help strengthen the LSH fields: 1) Harmonisation of good data stewardship and data access practices; 2) Enhancement of the interoperability of digital solutions and resources; and 3) Strengthening the capacity and expertise base in digital research. A Programme Board has been installed for the TDCC-LSH that oversees and guides the implementation of the TDCC-LSH programme.

In this first phase of TDCC-LSH, we have taken the approach to strongly invest in establishing working relationships with major LSH community initiatives, most prominently via the large-scale research infrastructure initiatives (LSRIs), the Dutch node in the European research infrastructure for life sciences information (ELIXIR-NL), the Health-RI nodes (UMCs), the Dutch research data management and data steward community, as well as the national bioinformatics and computational biology community (BioSB). The TDCC-LSH activities primarily target domain-specific data professionals across data driven health and life sciences fields. Through close collaboration with the other two TDCCs (TDCC-NES and TDCC-SSH) and alignment with the activities organised by local DCCs (LDCC) established at many research organisations and data generating facilities, we keep connected to the more discipline-agnostic needs, challenges and solutions.

With the above stakeholders, the TDCC-LSH activities have meanwhile resulted in a varied range of community-based project initiatives, including the development of a nationwide FAIR Fellowship programme for life science data stewards at research performing organisations, building an LSH FAIR trainers network, as well as developing an ELIXIR-NL toolbox for bioinformatics software, and extending the BioSB course programme with AI-training for data scientists in health and life sciences, all of which will start in 2025. Further project initiatives will be evaluated by NWO soon to further fill the TDCC-LSH programme. Regarding the data stewardship community, we have joined forces with the Dutch Data Steward Interest Group (DSIG) and extended its scope by adding domain-specific meetings to the DSIG activities.

In summary, in the first two years, the TDCC-LSH has brought together large funded initiatives and expert communities to strengthen data driven health and life sciences in the Netherlands, both by network activities as well as developing collaborative project initiatives. Together we are ready for the next implementation phase of TDCC-LSH.

Thematic Digital Competence Centers (TDCCs)

As part of the Dutch Implementation Plan Investments Digital Research Infrastructure (2019)¹, three national-level Thematic Digital Competence Centres (TDCC) have been established for the scientific domains Life Sciences & Health (LSH), Natural & Engineering Sciences (NES) and Social Sciences & Humanities (SSH). The mission of the TDCCs is to tackle domain specific challenges in data driven science by a combination of network activities and dedicated project funding. In the period 2020-2021 all three TDCCs consulted their respective communities and defined a roadmap, which will guide the TDCC activities. The TDCCs are complementary to the already existing Local Digital Competence Centers (LDCC), which offer support on a local level to scientists and data stewards within their institute.

The TDCC-LSH programme started in September 2022. This document shows the progress for TDCC-LSH, for the period September 2022 – August 2024.

Figure 1: Main roles of the TDCCs

¹ <https://www.nwo.nl/en/researchprogrammes/implementation-plan-investments-digital-research-infrastructure>

TDCC-LSH ambitions, governance and strategy

The Thematic Digital Competence Center for Life Sciences & Health (TDCC-LSH) is coordinated by Health-RI, following the formal merger of DTL into Health-RI in 2022/2023, and its overarching goal is to advance the field of data driven health and life research by strengthening the digital competencies and digital practices across stakeholders in the broad Dutch research domains of life sciences and biomedical/health sciences.

A broad and extensive consultation process has been carried out among LSH stakeholders in 2021 and the assembled input has been translated into a TDCC-LSH roadmap² which has been approved by PC-GWI and NWO. The TDCC-LSH roadmap has been set up to help identify the main wide felt bottlenecks in the LSH field, as summarised in Figure 2 below, and a prioritisation of these bottlenecks with input of the community.

- FAIR data
 - Findability, accessibility, interoperability, reusability
- Software & Tools
 - Finding the right tool for the right job
 - Software sustainability
- ICT: computing & storage
 - Secure processing environments
- Human capital
 - Training & capacity building of digital experts
- Support from research funders
 - Improve conditions for good data stewardship
 - Rewards & recognition for FAIR
- Communication
 - Sharing of success stories, benefits of FAIR data
 - Community building

Figure 2: TDCC-LSH challenges as identified in the TDCC-LSH Roadmap (pp. 14-16)

TDCC-LSH ambitions and core activities

Based upon the above list of bottlenecks, three main ambitions have been formulated for TDCC-LSH:

² <https://www.nwo.nl/sites/nwo/files/media-files/Roadmap%20TDCC%20LSH.pdf>

1. Harmonisation of good data stewardship and data access practices;
2. Enhancement of the interoperability of digital solutions and resources; and
3. Strengthening the capacity and expertise base in digital research.

These ambitions help steer the activities of the TDCC-LSH team and programme using the instruments initially available, being network coordination funding and project funding from NWO, to strengthen the broader data driven health & life sciences field.

The following core tasks have been picked up in the first two years of the TDCC-LSH programme:

1. Strengthen the national network of digital experts through network activities
2. Strengthen exchange of and alignment on good data stewardship and data access practices
3. Strengthen exchange of and alignment on bioinformatics and computational biology solutions, through national and international expert networks
4. Facilitate/support alignment of stakeholders in prioritising shared challenges and solutions and translation towards community-based projects
5. Help organise activities to overcome shared bottlenecks through TDCC funding and associated calls.

TDCC-LSH has proposed three KPIs for an active TDCC-LSH network³:

- KPI1: TDCC-LSH Network activities (WHAT)
- KPI2: Engagement in/involvement of the stakeholders in TDCC-LSH activities (WITH WHOM)
- KPI3: Progress perceived by the TDCC-LSH stakeholders (OUTCOMES)

TDCC-LSH Governance

To oversee and help steer the TDCC-LSH activities in line with the TDCC-LSH Roadmap and to signal emerging challenges and help prioritise responses to address these, a dedicated TDCC-LSH Programme Board (PB, see also Appendix 1) has been set up. The TDCC-LSH Programme Board is also in charge of selecting community-driven projects that will be set up under the TDCC-LSH umbrella with support from NWO or other funders. The Programme Board is composed of members that represent major communities in the broad data driven Health and Life Sciences research domain. These include a representative from each of the four groups of the Roadmap Large Scale Research infrastructures (LSRI), representatives from key national initiatives in the Life Sciences and Health domain, and NWO and ZonMw as observers. The TDCC-core team appointed at Health-RI supports the TDCC-LSH Programme Board in its role and the communication with the TDCC network. See Appendix 1 for more information about the TDCC-LSH Governance.

³ [KPIs TDCC-LSH network 2022-2024.pdf](#)

TDCC-LSH Strategy

The aim of TDCC-LSH is to strengthen the field of data driven health & life sciences together with the LSH field. The field of LSH is very broad, with many subdomains that each involve a (sub)community of experts in that particular domain. We have taken the approach to strongly invest in establishing working relationships with major LSH community initiatives, most prominently the **LSRIs, BioSB and ELIXIR-NL**, which were all already identified in the TDCC-LSH roadmap. The other major stream of our activities is focussed on the **domain-specific data stewards employed at research performing organisations (RPOs)**. In summary, TDCC-LSH activities target **domain specific data professionals across data driven health and life sciences fields**

LSRI initiatives each run major funded projects that are meant to develop and provide access to advanced facilities, resources and services. They each have specialised in certain field-specific data types and target specific research communities to conduct research and promote innovation in their field⁴. Each LSRI represents a subdomain of LSH and has set up or will set up infrastructure elements specifically needed for their field. Each LSRI is in close contact with their researchers and also are embedded in the international landscape. This makes the LSRI excellent partners for TDCC-LSH to connect to data stewards and researchers in the specific subdomains of LSH.

In the TDCC-LSH Programme Board we have appointed representatives of each of the 4 domains in the Domain Life & Medical Sciences of the LSRI roadmap. In this way we have ensured that the TDCC-LSH activities will be planned in line with the needs of the broader LSH field. In the proposed FAIR LSH fellowship programme (currently under review with NWO)⁵, we have engaged data experts from several LSRIs to act as coaches for the cohort of data stewards.

In line with the above, the national LSRI roadmap for 2021-2025 asks the research field to further intensify coordination and (interdisciplinary) collaborations and encourages cross-domain initiatives. This is completely in line with the ambitions of the TDCC-LSH to engage all stakeholders across the subdomains in LSH to discuss common challenges as identified in the TDCC-LSH roadmap, and work towards harmonization and joint solutions.

BioSB⁶, the national community of Bioinformatics and Systems Biology expert groups at universities, UMCs and institutes, focuses on knowledge exchange and training in bioinformatics and systems biology across research organisations in the Netherlands. BioSB activities cover a broad spectrum of application areas in diverse LSH subdomains. In the TDCC-LSH roadmap, BioSB was identified as an important stakeholder to engage in designing a national programme to strengthen the field of data driven health and life sciences research. BioSB expert groups help develop novel methodology and

⁴ https://www.nwo.nl/sites/nwo/files/media-files/National%20Roadmap%20for%20Large-scale%20Research%20Infrastructure%202021_0.pdf

⁵ Note: the FAIR LSH Fellowship Project has been approved by NWO in October 2024

⁶ <https://www.dtls.nl/biosb/>

educate the next generation of data scientists and computational biology experts across the LSH field of stakeholders.

ELIXIR, as the backbone RI for the wide Life and Medical Science domain, is crucial for the Dutch LSH researchers. It ensures that data produced across European institutions remains findable, accessible and interoperable, and thereby ensures that it can be reused by any researcher from any LSH discipline. Health-RI hosts the Dutch Node of ELIXIR (ELIXIR-NL⁷). In the TDCC-LSH roadmap ELIXIR-NL was identified as one of the pillars to the TDCC-LSH programme, connecting Dutch expertise, digital resources and tools to the European research community and vice versa help make available European resources to the Dutch life science and health community.

In addition to targeting the stakeholders at the organisational level, we also are actively involved in connecting to the community in a more bottom-up fashion. Again, the majority of our efforts here are focussed on the domain-specific issues. Through close collaboration with the other two TDCCs (TDCC-NES and TDCC-SSH) and alignment with the activities organised by local DCCs (LDCC) established at many research organisations or data generating facilities, we keep connected to the more discipline-agnostic needs, challenges and solutions.

In the following sections we will highlight both the network activities as well as the project related activities of TDCC-LSH. Detailed information about both streams of activities can be found in Appendix 2 (Network activities) and Appendix 3 & 4 (Projects).

⁷ <https://www.health-ri.nl/en/elixir>

TDCC-LSH network activities

TDCC-LSH Stakeholders

The TDCC-LSH network activities are aimed at strengthening and harmonising the digital practices among stakeholders in the broad Dutch LSH research domain. The main groups of stakeholders that have been identified for TDCC-LSH in the TDCC-LSH KPI document⁸ are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: TDCC-LSH Stakeholder groups. Overview of stakeholder groups with which TDCC-LSH has been liaising in the period September 2022 - August 2024. More details can be found in Appendix 2a.

⁸ [KPIs TDCC-LSH network 2022-2024.pdf](#)

Building on the pre-existing networks of data-driven life sciences (DTL) and health (Health-RI), the TDCC-LSH team has meanwhile been liaising with representatives of all stakeholder groups. Categories of activities that have been undertaken are:

1. Organising community workshops and events, often in co-creation with other stakeholders such as the other two TDCCs. The purpose of these meetings has been to connect initiatives actively to the TDCC(-LSH) network and to offer a showcase platform for initiatives addressing data challenges that fit the roadmap of the TDCC.
2. Presentations, webinars, Q&A sessions etc. either during national and international events organized by other parties or organised specifically by TDCC-LSH. The purpose of this outreach is to share the TDCC outcomes and start discussions about common challenges and collaborative approaches to tackle them. Several of these activities were done in collaboration with the other 2 TDCCs (see also further in the section *Cross-domain community activities with the other TDCCs*).
3. Dedicated meetings with representatives of specific stakeholders, for example with potential applicants in the context of the TDCC-LSH challenge project call, with the LDCCs and in one-on-one meetings with members of the TDCC-LSH community.

Below, highlights of activities for specific stakeholder groups and the outcomes are shown. A detailed overview of TDCC-LSH events and presentations mentioned under bullet 1 & 2 can be found in Appendix 2.

Research Performing Organisations (RPOs)

RPOs and their Local DCCs

One of our priorities has been to set good working relations with the RPOs, to understand how the local support is organised, how best to communicate and collaborate, to define our mutual roles and assess each other's strengths and challenges.

Local Digital Competence Centers (LDCCs)

In 2020, as part of the Dutch Implementation Plan Investments Digital Research Infrastructure (2019) which also describes the formation of the three national-level Thematic Digital Competence Centres (TDCCs)⁹, NWO provided impulse funding for the development of Local Digital Competence Centres (LDCCs) at research performing organisations, currently mainly universities, UMCs, and a shared DCC for NWO Institutes and for universities of applied sciences.

⁹ [Implementation Plan Investments Digital Research Infrastructure | NWO](#)

The LDCCs provide the necessary local research data support and maintain a local network of generic and domain specific data stewards; research software engineers; and ICT experts. They have strong knowledge of local generic services (e.g generic digital expertise & tooling) and are well aware of the general bottlenecks that researchers encounter during their daily research practices.

Because the TDCCs have a domain-specific focus and also aim to work cross-institute and on a national level, the LDCCs and TDCCs have a complementary role. For example, issues related to metadata standards for specific data types and subdomains of LSH need to be addressed at the cross-institute/national/international level. Here the TDCC-LSH can play a role by connecting research groups of RPOs and joining forces in the framework of international research data initiatives. This is illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Complementary role of LDCCs, TDCCs and e-infrastructure providers. The networks of the TDCCs connect scientists in their respective science fields across research organisations and cross-link to field initiatives and (international) research infrastructures.

To establish close collaboration with the LDCCs, the TDCCs undertook a series of roadshow visits to the majority of the LDCCs, including DCC-PO and DCC NWO-i. These visits were meant to learn more about each other's organisational structures, roadmaps and networks; to directly engage with domain

specific data stewards or local support professionals; to explore potential collaboration opportunities and to optimise communication flows between the national and local networks. This is especially important because there is not one LDCC model and many of the LDCCs are structured in a different way. Starting from Aug 2023, the installed LDCC liaison (stationed at SURF) joined these TDCC roadshow visits as well. Overall, the visits were very well received, the additional information was much appreciated and brought about positive relations between the networks.

A close collaboration has also been set up with LCRDM. The LCRDM network organizes monthly standup meetings for the Digital Competence Center Implementation Network (DCC-IN), which focuses on aligning agendas and promoting knowledge exchange between all the LDCCs. The TDCCs have taken up a regular seat during these DCC-IN standup meetings. In the context of this collaboration several events have been organised together with LCRDM and the other TDCCs (see further below in the section *Cross-domain community activities with the other TDCCs* and also Appendix 2a).

In general, the LDCC coordinators and the data stewards welcome the TDCC as an opportunity, although the current workload in the LDCCs is sometimes perceived as an obstacle for collaboration. The LDCC's put forward domain specific issues that they may not have the expertise or capacity to address themselves or that would benefit from a national approach. These issues include topics that are more generic such as the development of RDM processes and infrastructure (e.g. Yoda/iRODs) or the use of Electronic Lab Notebook systems. These are examples of topics that should be addressed by TDCCs and LDCCs jointly. Other challenges that are reported by the data stewards in the institutes are related to raising awareness among researchers as well as motivating them to implement responsible data practices. Here the TDCC-LSH can help by showcasing best practices with the help of the LSH community, see also the challenges identified with the LSRI's below. Issues related to metadata standards for specific subdomains of LSH need to be addressed at the cross-institute/national/international level and here TDCC-LSH can play a role.

One of the ways in which the TDCC LSH choses to address the challenges and themes identified by the RPOs is, as described further below, by designing a FAIR LSH Fellowship project (using NWO bottleneck funding for TDCC-LSH) that involves domain-specific data stewards at the research performing organisations. We will involve the local DCC of each RPO in this project.

BioSB: bioinformatics and systems biology

As indicated above (under TDCC-LSH strategy), one of the priorities of TDCC-LSH in the first phase has been to (further) engage with and support the BioSB and ELIXIR-NL community. To strengthen the involvement of BioSB, the Dutch national community of bioinformaticians and computational (systems) biology groups in the TDCC-LSH programme and the link to ELIXIR, the European backbone

data infrastructure for life sciences ELIXIR, the TDCC-LSH team has tasked dedicated community managers to help liaise with BioSB¹⁰ and ELIXIR.

BioSB, the national community of Bioinformatics and Systems Biology expert groups at universities, UMCs and institutes, is an important stakeholder for TDCC-LSH. BioSB focuses on knowledge exchange and training in bioinformatics and systems biology across research organisations in the Netherlands. TDCC-LSH is supporting BioSB with the organisation of BioSB events, most prominently the annual BioSB conference¹¹, but also the Hot Topics¹² meetings and the meetings for the YoungCB¹³ group of PhD students in bioinformatics and systems biology.

As part of the TDCC-LSH ambition to strengthen capacity-building and tooling in data driven and digital health and life sciences research, the TDCC-LSH team has supported BioSB to strengthen their cross-domain training and coaching programme in bioinformatics and computational biology. These activities will be supported through a TDCC-LSH challenge project (see further below, this project is currently submitted to NWO). In addition, BioSB, together with ELIXIR-NL, is partner in another TDCC-LSH challenge project related to developing a FAIR tool framework for bioinformatics services, tools and workflows in digital Life Sciences and Health (LSH) research (see further in the section *TDCC-LSH challenge projects call (2023-2024)*).

Outreach to research communities

The TDCC-LSH also extended its outreach to researchers by attending events that are frequently visited by researchers, such as NWO-Life conferences 2023 and 2024. The overall goal was to make researchers more aware of the TDCC-LSH network, roadmap and activities, and to make the research communities aware of tangible funding calls addressing the challenges described in the TDCC-LSH roadmap.

Research Supporting Organisations (RSOs)

RSOs: SURF, eScience Center, RDNL

The e-infrastructure services offered by SURF and eScience Center are a crucial part of the Dutch infrastructure landscape (see also Figure 4). In addition, SURF plays a role in coordination of the LDCCs and their projects. For these reasons SURF and eScienceCenter are important stakeholders for TDCC-LSH and we are working together with them and exploring where we can join forces. Just like Health-

¹⁰ <https://www.dtls.nl/biosb/>

¹¹ <https://www.aanmelder.nl/biosb2024>

¹² <https://www.dtls.nl/biosb/hottopics/>

¹³ <https://www.dtls.nl/youngcb/>

RI, SURF is also one of the partners of RDNL, with whom we collaborate closely to professionalise data stewardship in the Netherlands.

SURF

We have had recurring meetings with SURF, in different compositions, both with the other TDCCs and in the context of TDCC-LSH / Health-RI. We have explored ideas and collaborations around training and innovation and participate in SURF's reproducibility working group to identify opportunities for life science and health communities. We have been keen to ensure that RSOs such as SURF are involved in an early stage in the challenge projects and from their side, SURF agreed to point future relevant starting research projects to the TDCC-LSH.

We have established a close working relationship with the Life science and Health Research Partnership leads of SURF. The TDCCs have also aligned and provided input for the upcoming SURF LDCC Program, which is also part of the Dutch Implementation Plan Investments Digital Research Infrastructure (2019) and describes the technically facilitating and coordinating role of SURF in providing a secure, federated system that interconnects the DCCs. The SURF LDCC Program proposes a programmatic approach with a clearly defined goal based on bottlenecks. The program lines, approach and governance are aligned with the LDCCs via the LDCC Implementation network, the TDCCs and Open Science NL in the event of overlapping goals.

eScienceCenter

The research software engineers (RSE) are an important community mentioned in the TDCC-LSH roadmap. Hence, several meetings have taken place with the Life Sciences department and the Community Management & Communication team leads. The goal was to align relevant strategies with regards to eScienceCenter LSH projects, open science and Digital Competence Centers. Potential topics to collaborate that were identified and will be further explored are 1) Training & Capacity Building e.g. Co-organizing LSH specific editions of the newly developed eScience Center training for research support programme; 2) co-organize LSH specific RSE meetings for/with RSE-NL network; 3) Improving the findability and visibility of the Dutch LSH registries of specific software, tools and resources. Activities that were undertaken are the co-organisation of an RSE-NL/DSIG/TDCC-LSH meeting in April 2023¹⁴ and facilitating involvement of eScienceCenter fellows in relevant TDCC-LSH challenge projects. We assisted one of the eScience Center fellows in setting up a community of research software consultants in academic hospitals by co-organising a kick-off event in October 2024.

RDNL

RDNL is a collaboration of Research Supporting Organisations SURF, DANS, 4TU Research Data and Health-RI of which the three latter are not by chance the coordinating organisations of the three TDCCs. RDNL plays an important role in professionalising data stewardship in the Netherlands by

¹⁴ <https://nl-rse.org/events/2023-04-19-meetup>

organising three data management courses for starting data professionals per year, Essentials 4 Data Support (E4DS)¹⁵. In the past 10 years hundreds of new and aspiring data professionals have participated in the training, either by studying the publicly available materials online at their own pace or by subscribing to an intensive six week course.

The course not only lays a solid basis in responsible data management but also introduces the participants to the relevant Dutch communities for data professionals, such as the Data Stewards Interest Group. Although the course is in principle domain agnostic, it offers the opportunity to meet experts and peers from similar organisations and domains. The Health-RI FAIR data stewards basics course builds on the E4DS, elaborating on domain specific aspects of RDM and FAIR implementation, and introducing tools and workflows that are specific for the health domain.

The NPOS ambition to help drive capacity building in FAIR-based data stewardship¹⁶ is given an important impulse through the funding Open Science NL is making available for a national training and community programme for data stewardship¹⁷. In Summer 2024, the RDNL partners (SURF, DANS, 4TU.ResearchData and Health-RI) have submitted a proposal to set up a curriculum based on the job profiles at the Dutch RPOs. This curriculum will need to align with other training providers in the Netherlands to ensure a coherent and harmonised offering that covers different levels, specialised topics and domains. The TDCC-LSH role can be to assist in generic training and community-aspects, and specifically to address data stewardship and FAIR implementation strategies specific to common LSH-domain-data types (e.g multi-omics, imaging). Skilled and motivated staff are pivotal in realising the TDCC LSH ambitions and for the success of the challenge projects.

National Infrastructures

Large scale research infrastructures (LSRI)

The ambitions of the TDCC-LSH are also in line with the National Roadmap for Large-Scale Research Infrastructures (LSRIs) as described by NWO for the period 2021-2025. LSRI initiatives are facilities, resources and services used by a research community to conduct research and promote innovation in their field. The national roadmap for 2021-2025 asks the research field to further intensify coordination and (interdisciplinary) collaborations and encourages cross-domain initiatives. This is completely in line with the ambitions of the TDCC-LSH to harmonize all stakeholders across the domain. Hence, an active working collaboration is being developed with several LSRI and their data

¹⁵ <https://researchdata.nl/en/services/cursus/>

¹⁶ https://www.openscience.nl/sites/open_science/files/media-files/final_npos2030_ambition_document_and_rolling_agenda.pdf

¹⁷ https://www.openscience.nl/sites/open_science/files/media-files/Work%20programme%202024-2025.pdf

professionals, to align their ambitions with those of the TDCC-LSH to optimally use existing resources and (human) capital. It is our aim to, together with the field, help create a chain of interoperable 'learning systems'¹⁸ across life sciences & health, each involving different communities and stakeholders, but creating a similar – interoperable - data driven research ecosystem.

In the first two years of TDCC-LSH we have established working relations with several of the NWO Roadmap-funded LSRI's (o.a. NPEC, NEMI, NL-Bioimaging, UNLOCK, ARISE, X-Omics) and of course with Health-RI (a LSRI funded from the Growth Fund). In this first phase we have focussed on the already established LSRI's, and have also started contacts with emerging LSRI's (eg. LTERLife). Two dedicated LSRI meetings were held in Spring 2023 where several invited LSRI's (e.g. ARISE, BBMRI-NL, NEMI, NL-Bioimaging-AM, X-Omics, NPEC, UNLOCK, BSL3 Biosafety lab, u-NMR-NL Grid and Health-RI) shared their challenges, needs and solutions, such as for a) Making data FAIR at the source b) how to convince researchers that it is beneficial to make their data FAIR c) how to make data resources and infrastructures sustainable d) lack of a comprehensive overview of the current landscape (e.g. tools, trainings, FAIR experts, standards) for more details see Appendix 2B. Following up on these meetings several conversations have taken place with individual LSRI's. Two concrete follow-up activities consisted of a co-organised workshop in July 2023 with the Green Life Sciences community (NPEC, UNLOCK, ARISE, LTERlife) and a workshop co-organised in May 2024 with the Biodiversity community (ARISE, LTERlife). These workshops focused on a joint strategy approach for a foundational infrastructure (RDM, Data Storage, HPC, IAM, PID, FAIR) and knowledge exchange of experiences and technology. More information can be found in Appendix 2B. Other connections of TDCC-LSH with the LSRI's are their role as coaches in the LSH FAIR fellowship bottleneck project (see further below), their involvement in TDCC-LSH challenge projects, as well as the appointment of LSRI cluster representatives in the Programme Board of TDCC-LSH.

As described further below, we have chosen to design a FAIR LSH Fellowship project (using NWO bottleneck funding for TDCC-LSH) that involves data experts of several LSRI teams to train and coach the FAIR LSH fellows.

International Infrastructures

International connections & positioning: ELIXIR and EOSC

Strengthening alignment with and making bridges between domain specific international and national developments is very important. This will enable adoption of globally developed standards and best practices in digital life science and health research and is in line with European ambition to accelerate the digital transition. Through its positioning of TDCC-LSH in the Health-RI organisation, TDCC-LSH is very well connected to all European developments relevant for the LSH domain and is able to

¹⁸ inspired by the term "Learning Health(-care) System" used in the biomedical/healthcare domain

contribute to the realisation of strong - and where needed harmonised - practices in digital life sciences and health research, in alignment with international initiatives.

Research Infrastructures: ELIXIR & ELIXIR-NL

ELIXIR, as the backbone RI for the wide Life and Medical Science domain, is crucial for the Dutch researchers. It ensures that data produced across European institutions remains findable, accessible and interoperable, and thereby ensures that it can be reused by any researcher from any LSH discipline. Health-RI hosts the Dutch Node of ELIXIR (ELIXIR-NL¹⁹) and plays a leading role in several ELIXIR activities in the area of Data Stewardship and Data Management. For example, ELIXIR-NL / TDCC-LSH staff has led the training & capacity building work in the ELIXIR-CONVERGE project (2020-2023)^{20, 21} and is currently co-leading the ELIXIR Europe Research Data Management Community.^{22, 23} The TDCC-LSH team is working closely with the ELIXIR-NL Node Coordinator (stationed at Health-RI) as well as with members of the ELIXIR-NL community. TDCC-LSH was also presented by a poster at the ELIXIR All Hands Meeting in Uppsala in June 2024.²⁴

As part of the TDCC-LSH ambition to strengthen the international alignment of the Dutch field and create a toolbox for bioinformatics, and drawing on the capacities of the Dutch bioinformatics and computational biology groups to develop advanced tooling for life sciences research, the national node community of ELIXIR has, together with BioSB and supported by RSE-NL, proposed to set up a process to create an overview of Dutch-made tools and derived services available to the life science community, to help enhance the outreach to the Dutch research community and to the European field. With support of the TDCC-LSH team this has evolved to a successful TDCC-LSH Challenge project (see further below).

European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)

Another strong European connection is to EOSC, the European Open Science Cloud. Health-RI (and previously DTL) is very active in the EOSC ecosystem, where we follow the developments and align where relevant. In the area of Data Stewardship the Network Manager of TDCC-LSH has been co-chairing the EOSC-Association Task Force Data Stewardship, curriculum and career paths (2022-2024) and is currently co-leading the EOSC-A Opportunity Area Expert Group on Skills, Training, Rewards, Recognition & Upscaling (OAS).²⁵ Furthermore the TDCC-LSH Data stewardship Lead is member of the EOSC-A Task Force FAIR metrics and digital objects, and another Health-RI colleague is member of the EOSC-A Health Data Task Force.

¹⁹ <https://www.health-ri.nl/en/elixir>

²⁰ <https://elixir-europe.org/about-us/how-funded/eu-projects/converge/wp2>

²¹ <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.8348285>

²² <https://f1000research.com/articles/13-230/v1>

²³ <https://elixir-europe.org/communities/research-data-management>

²⁴ <https://doi.org/10.7490/f1000research.1119853.1>

²⁵ <https://eosc.eu/eosc-opportunity-area-expert-groups/>

The data stewardship theme featured also prominently in the 2023 and 2024 EOSC national tripartite events, where the Dutch EOSC members gathered together with representatives of the European Commission and the EOSC-Association Board. In both events the TDCCs were presented.^{26, 27} We make sure that our work is visible nationally and internationally, 2023 examples being the EOSC Symposium 2023²⁸ and the Open Science FAIR 2023²⁹ (both in Madrid), and the CoRDI 2023 (NFDI) conference in Karlsruhe³⁰. Finally, a recent discussion in EOSC is the establishment of EOSC Nodes (national, institutional, thematic) and also of a network of competence centers (by the Skills4EOSC project). Since TDCC-LSH is a thematic national competence center, we are monitoring these developments closely, a.o. by liaising with the Skills4EOSC project, with the aim of positioning ourselves properly in the emerging EOSC ecosystem.

Datastewards

Domain-specific data stewards and other professionals in data driven health and life sciences

The TDCC-LSH has contributed to building capacity and professionalising data stewardship at Dutch RPOs by organising domain specific meetings in the framework of the Data Stewards Interest Group (DSIG); by making data stewards and their contribution to data driven LSH research more visible, by organising events to draw attention to the formal embedding of data stewards in RPOs and their recognition and career paths (see further below).

Data Stewards Community: Data Stewards Interest Group (DSIG)

In June 2017 the Data Stewards Interest Group (DSIG)³¹ was initiated by members of Leiden UMC, UMC Utrecht, and DTL. The DSIG is an informal and inclusive data stewardship community open to everyone who is interested and promotes peer-learning through knowledge and experience exchange. Besides six to eight (online) meetings and events yearly, the DSIG has a mailing list and an active online presence through the Slack platform. The distinctive feature of the DSIG in comparison to other initiatives regarding data stewardship is the hands-on and solution-oriented approach for practical matters. To allow variety and include the various local activities on data stewardship, each meeting is organised and chaired by a different organisation but with fixed agenda items.

²⁶ <https://eosc.eu/news/national-tripartite-event-netherlands>

²⁷ <https://eosc.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/03/7-9-NL-EOSC-NTE-TDCCs-Yeomans-Arlinghaus-Gelderpdf.pdf>

²⁸ <https://symposium23.eoscfuture.eu/symposium/skills-training/>

²⁹ <https://www.opensciencefair.eu/workshops/digital-skills-for-fair-and-responsible-open-science-co-creating-the-content-structure-and-pathways>

³⁰ <https://tdcc.nl/connections-at-cordi-for-data-stewardship-training-and-for-tdcc-lsh-life-sciences-amp-health/>

³¹ <https://tdcc.nl/dsig/>

From the transition of DTL into Health-RI, the DSIG has been actively facilitated by the Health-RI FAIR team linked closely to the TDCC-LSH team. Formally as of May 2023, the three Thematic Digital Competence Centres (TDCCs) have joined forces with the DSIG and started hosting meetings on domain specific topics (LSH/NES/SSH). Hence, general meetings now alternate with domain specific meetings. 12 meetings were organised in the period of 2023- July 2024,³² of which three were LSH domain specific. The themes of these meetings were FAIR lesson plans, Personal Health Train and a joint meeting of Research Software Engineers and the DSIG. Besides special topics, the agenda always allows time for participants to share news and successes and for an overview of the 10 most noteworthy events or developments of interest for the community.

In July 2024, the DSIG Slack had almost 1000 members (of which 80 active members), both from within and outside the Netherlands. The monthly meetings are attended on average by 35 people, with some meetings attracting over 50 people. With its mailing list, slack channel and regular meetings, the DSIG is a strong communications channel for the TDCCs to connect to individual data stewards in the Netherlands and beyond.

Spotlight on: data stewards

Every other week, the Thematic DCCs and the DSIG publish an interview on the TDCC website that puts the spotlight on one research data steward working in the Netherlands, to stimulate knowledge exchange and peer-to-peer learning³³. It is one of the instruments to increase the visibility of data stewards and their contribution to data driven research.

Figure 5: Spotlight on data stewards series: 3 examples from the LSH field³⁴

³² <https://tdcc.nl/dsig/dsig-meetings/>

³³ <https://tdcc.nl/category/spotlight-on>

³⁴ <https://tdcc.nl/dsig/spotlight-on-data-stewards/>

Professionalisation of data stewardship in the Netherlands

Two years after the publication of the NPOS report on Professionalizing Data Stewardship³⁵, we organized the workshop *Building capacity for data stewardship in the Netherlands: formal job profiles, training and career perspective* that took place in Utrecht in April 2023.^{36, 37}

The discussion was centred around the current situation and next steps for five recommendations from the report: formalisation of the job profile, organisation of data stewards, data stewards' capacity, availability of training and career perspectives for data stewards. One of the conclusions was that data stewards are now better visible and partly formally embedded in three types of RPO's in the Netherlands (Universities, University Medical Centers and Universities of Applied Sciences) but that there still is a need for more capacity, certified training and attractive career paths. More detailed information about the workshop is given in Appendix 2b.

In November 2024 we will co-organise a workshop on the recognition of data professionals during the national Recognition & Rewards Festival.³⁸

Policy Drivers

Funders

Advancing digital research in the broader LSH domain involves contributions at many levels. The TDCC-LSH aims to involve policymakers and funders, who can help influence the digital life sciences & health landscape. As stakeholders they have an important role since they set the requirements for good data stewardship and jointly have the position to help create the right boundary conditions for digital research in the life sciences & health domain.

NWO

NWO is not only the funder of the TDCC-LSH programme but is also very engaged and involved in both the ambitions and strategy as well as the procedures/processes related to TDCC-LSH. During the TDCC-LSH roadmap phase (2020-2021) NWO provided support in the role of a secretary to the leads ("trekkers") of the roadmap, who also was co-author of the roadmap. After the start of TDCC-LSH in September 2022, the NWO secretary stayed involved and contributed to monthly meetings with the trekkers and the TDCC-LSH team. On the operational level two other NWO colleagues are in close

³⁵ Professionalising data stewardship in the Netherlands. Competences, training and education. Dutch roadmap towards national implementation of FAIR data stewardship, Mijke Jetten et al. (2021) <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.4320504>

³⁶ <https://tdcc.nl/building-capacity-for-data-stewardship-in-the-netherlands-formal-job-profiles-training-and-career-perspective/>

³⁷ <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.8026658>

³⁸ <https://recognitionrewards.nl/festival/recognition-rewards-festival-2024/>

contact with the three TDCCs in a 3-weekly operational meeting. Together, NWO and TDCCs shaped the procedures and processes for the bottleneck project and the challenge projects. On a strategic level, quarterly meetings take place with the TDCC teams, the trekkers and the secretaries. Finally, the Digitalisation Research Advisory Committee (Committee DO)³⁹ is formally responsible for overseeing the TDCC programme.

ZonMw

Since the start of the TDCC-LSH roadmap phase (2021) ZonMw has been actively involved and has provided one of the secretaries of the leads (“trekkers”) of the roadmap. Since ZonMw is the major funder in the Health domain in the Netherlands its involvement is crucial for TDCC-LSH.

In 2024 we started the conversation with ZonMW to discuss how TDCC LSH’s network activities and projects benefit ZonMW funded research projects and contribute to the goals of ZonMW’s policy for data management and FAIR data⁴⁰ and future roadmap, e.g. by increasing the capacity and expertise in RPOs.

Open Science NL

The NPOS2030 Ambition Document and Rolling Agenda⁴¹ was published in 2022 and was followed by the start of Open Science NL in 2023⁴². In the OpenScience NL work programme⁴³ themes Capacity Building, interoperability, FAIR data and Open Science infrastructure have a prominent place and these align very well with the TDCC-LSH ambitions. There is also specific support from Open Science NL for the TDCCs, for example the call to strengthen the interoperability expertise in each TDCC-LSH⁴⁴. As coordinator of the TDCC-LSH, Health-RI has been one of the national signatories of the Open Science Covenant, and takes part in OSNL bestuurlijk overleg (incl. preparatory and follow-up meetings).

³⁹ <https://www.nwo.nl/en/news/new-digitalisation-research-advisory-committee>

⁴⁰ <https://www.zonmw.nl/en/everything-about-fair-data-management>

⁴¹ <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.7433766>

⁴² <https://www.openscience.nl/>

⁴³ https://www.openscience.nl/sites/open_science/files/media-files/Work%20programme%202024-2025.pdf

⁴⁴ <https://www.openscience.nl/en/calls/strengthening-local-and-thematic-dccs-software-training-and-data-interoperability>

TDCC-NES & TDCC-SSH

Cross-domain community activities with the other TDCCs

A close working relationship and collaboration with the network managers and community coordinators of TDCC-NES and TDCC-SSH have been established since the start of the TDCCs. The three TDCCs have regular meetings together to harmonize best practices across the three domains. The TDCCs also form a coherent front and together organize roadshow tours, workshops, attend conferences and coordinate outreach and communication through the TDCC website. The TDCCs aim is to work closely together but still acknowledge and accommodate the different needs of the scientific domains covered by each respective TDCC. Hence, a certain divergence between the networks might occur over time, as the projects, priorities, and communities further develop.

TDCC website

At the end of 2022 the TDCC logo and website (<https://tdcc.nl/>) have been developed and established. The TDCC website domain is hosted by SURF. The corporate identity and logos have been incorporated on the website. Over time the website has been professionalised and branded communication materials have been developed. The website now features information about the specific TDCC domains, their roadmaps, network, projects, calls, has regular blog posts and features the latest information regarding TDCC-related events. It also features the agenda and notes of DSIG community meetings⁴⁵, and, as already described above, has a "Spotlight on data stewards" published interview series. All three TDCCs offer a possibility for individuals or organisations to register their interest in one or more TDCCs.

TDCC community events

Together with the other two TDCCs, several community events have been organized in the first two years to exchange best practices between domains, harmonize data stewardship on a national level and to find cross-domain synergy between organizations. Several events that were co-organized by the three TDCCs include the: *"The DCC Network, Who are we?, how do we operate and how do we collaborate with each other?"* workshop on the 15th of March 2023 that was organized together with

⁴⁵ <https://tdcc.nl/dsig/>

the TDCCs and LDCCs;⁴⁶ "Addressing bottlenecks together to encourage FAIR practice in research methods, data, and software" workshop on the 31st of August 2023 organized by the three TDCC domains during the Open Science Festival; and the "Teaming up across domains" event organized by the TDCCs & LCRDM network on 27th of February 2024, for more detailed description of these events, see Appendix 2b.

⁴⁶ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7735865>

TDCC-LSH projects

Strengthening the Dutch LSH FAIR data stewardship landscape – installing a national cohort of FAIR LSH fellows

One of the elements of the TDCC project funding by NWO is the so-called “bottle neck” funding, where each TDCC can apply for projects, with a total budget up to 1 Meuro, that tackle the prioritised bottlenecks that have been identified in the TDCC roadmaps.⁴⁷

The TDCC-LSH bottleneck funding will be used for a single integrated project: "Strengthening the Dutch LSH FAIR data stewardship landscape – installing a national cohort of FAIR LSH fellows" (Figure 6). Each RPO can delegate a fellow (0,2 fte for 1 year) to participate in the programme and to tackle a use case that addresses one of the prioritised challenges in the TDCC-LSH roadmap. The challenges from the roadmap that were prioritized by the LSH community are related to 1) network building, 2) tools, resources & guidelines and 3) skill building.

The main objectives of the FAIR LSH fellowship programme are:

1. **Enhancing digital competencies across Dutch Health & Life sciences** by skill building in FAIR data stewardship in the RPOs in the Netherlands
2. **Collaboratively develop solutions and resources related to FAIR implementation** in the LSH domain in the Netherlands
3. **Increase cross-domain collaboration in FAIR implementation** in the LSH domain by expanding and strengthening the network of FAIR LSH experts

The fellows will bring in their expertise in life sciences and/or health data handling, together covering multiple domains such as clinical, genomics, imaging etc. They will work simultaneously on advancing their own skills (with the commitment to spread this expertise in their own organisation) as well as working in a national context to tackle common challenges. The fellows will be guided by a team of coaches, who are all experts in their own (sub)domain of LSH and have an extensive track record in data generation, FAIRification, analysis and/or general data handling. We have secured participation of FAIR data experts from the LSRI, the Health-RI network and GOFAIR as coaches in our bottleneck project, who will guide the FAIR LSH fellows. The fields of expertise which are covered by the coaches teams are biodiversity, microbial data, bioimaging, genomics, rare diseases and plant phenotyping. The FAIR LSH fellows will also be supported by a dedicated training & capacity building programme.

A few examples of potential use cases to tackle these prioritised challenges are a) create overviews of tools, resources, experts, best practices and make these overviews findable and searchable; b) working towards establishing a community metadata standard for specific subdomain / data type; c)

⁴⁷ <https://www.nwo.nl/sites/nwo/files/media-files/Roadmap%20TDCC%20LSH.pdf>

establish FAIR implementation profiles; d) develop FAIR guidelines (for specific tools / data types / ...)
 e) develop training materials including advanced FAIR training; f) enable advocacy & awareness.

The TDCC-LSH FAIR fellowship project is currently under review with NWO.⁴⁸

Figure 6: The TDCC-LSH FAIR Fellowship programme

⁴⁸ Note: the TDCC-LSH FAIR fellowship project was approved by NWO in October 2024

TDCC-LSH challenge projects call (2023-2024)

TDCC-LSH challenge project process

The Dutch Research Council (NWO) had opened the first TDCC project call with a total budget of €1,600,000 per domain from November 15 2023 until November 15 2024 to support the TDCC network and the digitalization of science as a whole. Applicants were able to apply for a minimum total of €50,000 and a maximum of €400,000 for project proposals with a maximum duration of 24 months. In order to be able to apply for project funding at NWO, an application had to be accompanied by a submission letter from the responsible TDCC domain that was jointly signed by the TDCC domain leads. For this challenge projects call, TDCC-LSH developed an application and assessment process, which focused on connecting initiatives to strengthen project applications and prevent fragmentation of project funding. In total five Q&A information sessions were organised to inform the TDCC-LSH community about the application process. In addition, the TDCC-LSH team also provided further support and clarification on request of potential applicants.

The complete process was set-up in such a way that successful ideas would gradually require more time investment from the applicants, that proposals are co-developed from the start and are finalized at the end of the process and can be directly submitted to NWO. Briefly, interested applicants were asked to share their project ideas by submitting a short 'Expression of Interest' (Eoi) statement. The TDCC-LSH team would subsequently review the Eois, explore similar project ideas, provide matchmaking opportunities and give advice aimed at strengthening community-driven projects. Applicants were asked to refine their ideas and to translate their Eoi ideas into a pre-proposal. The TDCC-LSH Programme Board would evaluate the pre-proposal applications and select proposals to be rejected, revisited at a later stage or approved to proceed to a full proposal. Full project proposals had to be written following the application form format as provided by NWO and available in ISAAC. The TDCC-LSH Programme Board would review all final proposals and make a final decision, which proposals would eventually receive the TDCC-LSH letter of submission that is needed to complete the NWO call by submitting through ISAAC. See Appendix 3a for a detailed description of the process.

In the call of 2023-2024 a total of 22 project ideas (Eois) were submitted, 10 in the first round and 12 in the second round. Most of the projects requested almost the maximum budget available of €400,000, leading to a total requested budget amount of 7,35 million euro, making the total requested budget roughly 4,5x higher than the available budget of 1,6 million euro. This clearly indicates a huge interest from the LSH field. Per August 2024, 3 projects have been accepted by the TDCC-LSH Programme Board and received a TDCC-LSH recommendation letter and these 3 proposals are currently under review by NWO. See further below for more details about these proposals.

TDCC-LSH challenge project themes

All UMCs and most universities were involved in the project proposals. In several project proposals the Large-Scale Research Infrastructures (LSRIs), Research supporting organisations (RSOs) (i.e. e-Infrastructures), large consortia and companies were involved. A complete overview of all project ideas and the participating institutions can be found in Appendix 3b.

The word cloud in Figure 7 shows the keywords that the applicants of the challenge projects indicated in their proposal (details can be found in Appendix 3b). From the word cloud it is very clear that the proposed topics in the projects align with the ambitions and identified challenges in the TDCC-LSH roadmap.

Figure 7: Word cloud of the keywords of the applications of the TDCC-LSH challenge projects 2023-2024.

Selected TDCC-LSH challenge projects

As indicated above, the TDCC-LSH Programme Board is responsible for the selection of proposals that will receive a submission letter to accompany the application when submitted to NWO. It is important to note that important criteria were alignment with the TDCC-LSH roadmap and its identified ambitions as well as the way the applicants showed that their proposal is formulated in a community-driven process, involving the main parties in their subdomain of LSH. The full criteria can be found in the call text.⁴⁹

⁴⁹ https://www.nwo.nl/sites/nwo/files/media-files/TDCC%20call_for_proposals_EN-def2.pdf

In the first round of 2023/2024 the PB has selected three proposals. They are all covering the broad LSH field and the expectation is that this will yield the most impact. All results will become available for all subfields in LSH. Going forward, the PB will have to find the balance between selecting broader and more subdomain specific projects for LSH.

The following projects were accepted by the TDCC-LSH Programme Board in the first round of the 2023-2024 TDCC-LSH challenge projects call (for a complete overview and summary of the proposals, see Appendix 3b).

1. A FAIR tool framework for bioinformatics services, tools and workflows in digital Life Sciences and Health (LSH) research - Dr. H. Mouhib; Maastricht University (UM)
2. LEARN-FAIR: Life Science & Health Educational Alignment for Research and Networking in FAIR Data Management Dr. M.G. Kersloot; Amsterdam UMC (AUMC)
3. Training the next generation of FAIR-aware and AI-savvy data scientists for the LSH domain Dr. ir. P. Moerland; Amsterdam UMC (AUMC)

These 3 projects have been submitted to NWO in July 2024.⁵⁰ Additional TDCC-LSH challenge project(s) for the 2023-2024 project funding will be selected in October 2024 by the TDCC-LSH Programme Board, for submission to NWO in November 2024.

⁵⁰ Note: All three TDCC-LSH challenge projects have been approved by NWO in November 2024

Conclusion 2022-2024 & Outlook

Looking back on the first two years of TDCC-LSH, we can conclude that we have taken important steps regarding the TDCC-LSH roadmap ambitions. We are developing towards a platform that connects large funded initiatives and expert communities to strengthen data driven health and life sciences in the Netherlands.

The first two years (September 2022 - August 2024) focussed on building and strengthening the network, on preparations for the TDCC-LSH projects, as well as on formulating and submitting the first 4 TDCC-LSH projects. At the moment of writing (December 2024), it has become clear that all 4 projects have been approved and will start in 2025 with funding support by NWO. Going forward, we will move towards implementation and execution of the TDCC-LSH projects.

Major TDCC-LSH accomplishments for the period September 2022 - August 2024 include:

- Close collaboration with TDCC-NES and TDCC-SSH including a joint strategy for communication and outreach and alignment of processes and good working relations with the local DCCs
- The instalment of the TDCC-LSH Programme Board, that oversees and guides the TDCC-LSH activities. The PB is composed of members that represent major communities in the broad data driven Health and Life Sciences research domain, which secures that there is a good overview over the full LSH field and its data challenges.
- Strong working relationships with all major LSH stakeholders, whom we brought together to discuss joint data challenges and solutions to tackle them.
- Strengthening the Dutch Data Steward Interest Group (DSIG) and extension of its scope by adding domain-specific meetings to the DSIG activities
- A large number of TDCC-LSH (co-)organised events and outreach activities, again with the intention to bring experts together, share knowledge and expertise, facilitate discussions and collaborations
- Formulation of a FAIR LSH fellowship project, currently under review with NWO, where experts from a.o. the LSRI's will act as coaches for a Dutch cohort of fellows, containing one fellow from each Dutch RPO.
- The development and implementation of a transparent open call process for applying for TDCC challenge project funding, as well as facilitating stakeholders in preparing proposals. This process resulted in almost 20 project proposals, from very diverse subcommunities in LSH, indicating that there is a huge demand for funding mechanisms targeting data challenges related to the three ambitions of TDCC-LSH.
- Submission of three TDCC-LSH challenge projects by the LSH community (currently under review with NWO), tackling LSH broad issues related to the challenges as identified in the TDCC-LSH roadmap.

Looking back on the first two years of TDCC-LSH we have some reflections that will also guide us forward.

It is evident that the LSH field and the LSH network itself are continuously in motion, and so are the approaches, resources and needs and challenges related to data-driven research. Consequently, the TDCC-LSH will have to finetune its engagement strategy to fit this quickly evolving landscape. It is our aim to keep investing in the network and monitor how to best engage the full LSH domain, and also further develop ways to do so, taking into account the capacity of the TDCC-LSH core team. We will finetune our engagement strategy in the coming period.

Related to the current TDCC-LSH project funding stream through NWO, the broad interest and the number of proposals submitted prove that there is a real need for an instrument that enables infrastructure and support related projects to help strengthen research communities in their data driven research. The keywords from the submitted projects confirm that the priorities in the LSH field still match the ambitions of the roadmap: FAIR, workflows, metadata, capacity, interoperability, education, data stewardship, infrastructure, etc.

As the amount of funding applied for by the community largely exceeds the available funding, together with the field we need to reflect on ways to address this. One of the current thoughts is that the network coordination team will explicitly engage with the subcommunities that have applied for TDCC-LSH funding but were not successful in the first round and support them with network activities. This way we hope to maintain the momentum that has been created, realise synergies by connecting initiatives, and help build a common agenda with involvement of all relevant stakeholders.

Related to the next round of TDCC-LSH project funding we are currently discussing with NWO and the other two TDCCs to formulate the call text and conditions for the 2025 call for proposals. For this we will also use the lessons learned from the 2023-2024 call.

In conclusion, the first two years of TDCC-LSH have seen significant steps in building and strengthening the network, as we land initiating project proposals. In the coming period we will define our work plan for the coming years. TDCC-LSH will move towards the next phase, which will be more focused on working on solutions to the identified challenges, both within (funded) TDCC-LSH projects but also through (network) activities with specific stakeholders. Guided by the TDCC-LSH Programme Board, activities and priorities will be set taking into account the achievements, reflections and lessons learned listed above, and input and advice from advisory bodies such as the DO committee.

Appendices

Appendix 1: TDCC-LSH Governance

Appendix 2a: Overview TDCC-LSH network activities

Appendix 2b: TDCC-LSH events 2022-2024: detailed information

Appendix 3a: The TDCC-LSH challenge project process

Appendix 3b: Overview TDCC-LSH projects

Appendix 1: TDCC-LSH Governance

Figure 8: TDCC-LSH Governance

TDCC-LSH Programme Board

The Programme Board is composed of members that represent major communities in the broad data driven Health and Life Sciences research domain. Since the end of 2023 the TDCC-LSH Programme Board meets 3-4 times per year to review progress in the TDCC-LSH programme and guides the TDCC coordination team in its work with research communities in the LSH domain. NWO and ZonMw are observers of these Programme Board meetings. The TDCC-LSH Programme Board is also in charge of selecting community-driven projects that will be set up under the TDCC-LSH umbrella with funding support from NWO or other funders.

Composition of the TDCC-LSH Programme Board

- Representatives of each of the four groups of the Roadmap Large Scale Research infrastructures (LSRI):
 - LSRI-Group Health Sciences
 - LSRI-Group Medical Sciences
 - LSRI-Group Green Life Sciences
 - LSRI-Group Life Sciences & Enabling Technologies
- Representatives from key national initiatives in data driven health & life sciences:
 - BioSB (Bioinformatics and Systems Biology research and education)
 - ELIXIR-NL (national node of the European ELIXIR infrastructure for life sciences data)

- Health-RI (establishing the national health data infrastructure for research and innovation).
- Co-leads of the TDCC-LSH field consultation and Roadmap design appointed by NWO.
- Chair

TDCC-LSH Programme Board members (per August 2024):

- Prof. dr. Nine Knoers (Professor of Genetics, UMC Groningen, on behalf of LSRI - Health Sciences Group)
- Dr. ir. Koen Vincken (Associate Professor of Image Sciences Institute (ISI), UMC Utrecht, on behalf of LSRI - Medical Sciences Group)
- Prof. dr. Alain van Gool (Professor of Personalized Healthcare, Radboudumc, on behalf of LSRI - LSET Group)
- Prof. dr. Hauke Smidt (Professor of Molecular Ecology, Wageningen University, on behalf of LSRI - Green Life Sciences group)
- Prof. dr. Sanne Abeln (Professor of AI Technology for Life, Utrecht University, on behalf of BioSB)
- Prof. dr. Jaap Heringa (Professor of Bioinformatics, VU-university Amsterdam, on behalf of ELIXIR-NL)
- Prof. dr. Gerrit Meijer (Professor of Pathology, the Netherlands Cancer Institute (NKI), CSO and Board member at Health-RI).
- Dr. Ruben Kok (CSA and Board member at Health-RI, co-lead TDCC-LSH Roadmap, chair of the TDCC-LSH Programme Board)
- Prof. Dr. Vera van Noort (Professor of Computational Biology, Leiden University and Leuven University, co-lead TDCC-LSH Roadmap)

TDCC-LSH team

Financially supported by NWO to help strengthen digital research, a small team positioned at host organization Health-RI acts as the TDCC-LSH network coordination team. The TDCC-LSH coordination team informs all relevant stakeholders in the TDCC-LSH network and coordinates the TDCC-LSH programme. The TDCC-LSH coordination team also facilitates the community-driven project call process and guides or monitors the progress of TDCC-LSH projects and their selected project teams.

- Network manager: Dr. Celia van Gelder
- Community Coordinator Life Sciences: Kimberley Zwiers, MSc
- Community Coordinator Health: Dr. Fieke Schoots
- Community Manager BioSB: Petra Aarnoutse, BSc
- Community Manager: Dr. Meike Bungler
- FAIR data stewardship lead: Dr. Mijke Jetten
- TDCC-LSH roadmap author & Programme Board chair: Dr. Ruben Kok

Appendix 2a: Overview TDCC-LSH network activities

This appendix gives an overview of network activities of TDCC-LSH for the period September 2022 - August 2024. In addition, planned events for the second half of 2024 are also indicated.

Categories of activities that are listed are:

1. (Co-)organised events

Organising community workshops and events, often in co-creation with other stakeholders such as the other two TDCCs. The purpose of these meetings has been to connect initiatives actively to the TDCC(-LSH) network and to offer a showcase platform for initiatives addressing data challenges that fit the roadmap of the TDCC.

2. Outreach

Presentations, webinars, Q&A sessions etc. either during national and international events organized by other parties or organised specifically by TDCC-LSH. The purpose of this outreach is to share the TDCC outcomes and start discussions about common challenges and collaborative approaches to tackle them. Several of these activities were done in collaboration with the other 2 TDCCs

Note: Dedicated meetings with representatives of specific stakeholders, for example with potential applicants in the context of the TDCC-LSH challenge project call, with the LDCCs), and one-on-one meetings with members of the TDCC-LSH community are not listed in this table.

RPOs	<i>Research performing organisations (e.g. Universities, UMCs, research institutes, HBOs including their LDCCs.)</i>
RSOs	<i>Research supporting organisations (e.g. SURF, DANS, NLeSC, 4TU.ResearchData, etc.)</i>
National Infrastructures	<i>National domain-specific research infrastructure initiatives (e.g. health & life sciences LSRI-projects)</i>
International Infrastructures	<i>National node teams of European infrastructure initiatives (e.g. health & life sciences ESFRIs, EOSC, etc.)</i>
Data stewards	<i>Domain-specific data stewards and other professionals in data driven health and life sciences</i>
Policy Drivers	<i>Policy Drivers of digital technology, services and infrastructure</i>
TDCC- NES & TDCC-SSH	<i>Harmonisation with other TDCC domains</i>

TDCC-LSH Stakeholders

Figure 9: Enlargement of figure 3. TDCC-LSH Stakeholder groups. Overview of stakeholder groups with which TDCC-LSH has been liaising in the period 2022-2024.

Overview of (co-)organized events and outreach activities

Fig. 10: Overview of co-organised events and outreach activities indicating stakeholders involved

Name	Date	Location	Role	Stakeholders involved						
				Research Performing Organizations (RPOs)	National Supporting Organisations (NSOs)	International Infrastructures	Data stewards	Policy Drivers (e.g. funders)	TDCC-NES & TDCC-SSH	
2023										
Large Scale Research Infrastructure (LSRI) meeting - LSH domain	15 Feb 2023	Utrecht	Organizer							
BioSB HotTopics: Evolution in and of cell communities	15 Feb 2023	Amsterdam	Co-organizer							
LDCC's & TDCC's workshop (the DCC Network: Who we are, how we work)	15 Mar 2023	Utrecht	Organizer							
Data Stewards Job Profiles workshop	04 Apr 2023	Utrecht	Organizer							
Large Scale Research Infrastructure (LSRI) meeting - LSH domain	14 Apr 2023	Online	Organizer							
DSIG meeting - LSH domain specific (topic: Research Software)	19 Apr 2023	Online	Organizer							
FAIR trainers NL workshop	01 Jun 2023	Amsterdam	Co-organizer							
Green life Sciences Foundational Infrastructure workshop	12 Jul 2023	Utrecht	Co-organizer							
DSIG meeting - LSH domain specific (topic: Personal Health Train)	11 Sep 2023	Online	Organizer							
BioSB HotTopics: Computational Methods for Spatial data analysis	17 Nov 2023	Leiden	Co-organizer							
2024										
TDCC & LCRDM event: "Teaming Up Across Domains"	27 Feb 2024	Utrecht	Organizer							
DSIG meeting - LSH domain specific (topic: FAIR lesson plans)	06 Mar 2024	Online	Organizer							
BioSB HotTopics: (Generative) AI in Biology	27 Mar 2024	Amsterdam	Co-organizer							
BioSB YoungCB event	15 May 2024	Utrecht	Co-organizer							
Biodiversity & ecology data steward network workshop	17 May 2024	Utrecht	Co-organizer							
BioSB Conference 2024	18 - 19 Jun 2024	Egmond aan Zee	Co-organizer							
eScience Center Vantage6 Workshop	16 - 17 Oct 2024	Utrecht	Co-organizer							
DSIG meeting - LSH domain specific (topic: OS training & FAIR)	12 Sep 2024	Online	Organizer							
Workshop Research software management at Dutch UMCs	7 Oct 2024	Utrecht	Co-organizer							
BioSB HotTopics: Bioinformatics methods for pathogen surveillance	22 Oct 2024	Amsterdam	Co-organizer							
Recognition & Rewards Festival 2024 - workshop	08 Nov 2024	Ede	Co-organizer							

Name	Date	Location	Role	Stakeholders Involved					
Outreach (events attended) (26)				Research Performing Organizations (RPOs)	National Infrastructures	International Infrastructures	Data stewards	Policy Drivers (e.g. funders)	TDCC-NES & TDC-SSH
2022									
LCRDM networking days (workshop TDCC what is it for me)	01 Nov 2022	Utrecht	Speaker	█					
DTL Scientific Advisory Committee	15 Nov 2022	Utrecht	Speaker	█					
FAIR Data Day	29 Nov 2022	Utrecht	Participant	█					
2023									
FAIR for physical objects workshop	01 Mar 2023	Utrecht	Participant	█					
EOSC-NL Tripartite event	11 Apr 2023	Utrecht	Speaker			█			
WUR WDCC Meetup	20 Apr 2023	Wageningen	Speaker		█				
BioSB Conference 2023	9 - 10 May 2023	Egmond aan Zee	Participant, Poster						
NWO Life 2023	22 - 24 May 2023	Egmond aan Zee	Booth		█				
Open Science Festival 2023	31 Aug 2023	Rotterdam	Booth, Speaker						
CoRDI Conference	14 Sep 2023	Karlsruhe	Speaker						
EOSC Symposium 2023	20 - 22 Sep 2023	Madrid	Speaker						
Open Science FAIR	25 - 27 Sep 2023	Madrid	Speaker						
Health-RI Conference	12 Oct 2023	Utrecht	Booth						
DCC-IN meeting on workflows + career paths data stewards	06 Nov 2023	Utrecht	Moderator						
Benelux Metabolomics Days 2023	16 - 17 Nov 2023	Utrecht	Participant						
2024									
NWO - Large Scale Research Infrastructure (LSRI) IT workshop	14 Mar 2024	Utrecht	Participant						
X-Omics Festival	15 Apr 2024	Nijmegen	Booth						
National Research Software Days (eScience Center)	23 Apr 2024	Hilversum	Participant						
NWO Life 2024	21 - 23 May 2024	Egmond aan Zee	Booth & Pitch						
EOSC-NL Tripartite event	22 May 2024	Utrecht	Speaker						
SURF Research Days	30 May 2024	Amersfoort	Booth						
ELIXIR All Hands meetings	10 Jun 2024	Uppsala	Participant, Poster						
Benelux Metabolomics Days 2024	05 Sep 2024	Ghent	Participant						
Health-RI Conference	10 Oct 2024	Utrecht	Booth						
Open Science Festival 2024	22 Oct 2024	Maastricht	Booth						
EOSC Symposium 2024	22 Oct 2024	Berlin	Speaker						

Name	Date	Location	Role	Stakeholders Involved						
				Research Performing Organisations (RPOs)	Research Supporting Organisations (RSOs)	National Infrastructures	International Infrastructures	Data stewards	Policy Drivers (e.g. funders)	TDCC-NES & TDCC-SSH
DSIG Meetings across domains (8)										
2022										
DSIG meeting - across domains	27 Sep 2022	Online	Organizer	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
2023										
DSIG meeting - across domains	12 Jan 2023	Online	Organizer	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
DSIG meeting - across domains	16 Feb 2023	Online	Organizer	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
DSIG meeting - across domains	23 Mar 2023	Online	Organizer	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
DSIG meeting - across domains	16 May 2023	Online	Organizer	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
2024										
DSIG meeting - across domains	01 Feb 2024	Online	Organizer	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
DSIG meeting - across domains	02 Jul 2024	Online	Organizer	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
DSIG meeting - across domains	14 Oct 2024	Online	Organizer	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
TDCC-LSH Challenge project information sessions (5)										
2023										
Q&A Challenge projects - LSH Round 1	19 Dec 2023	Online	Webinar	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
Q&A Challenge projects - LSH Round 1	20 Dec 2023	Online	Webinar	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
2024										
Q&A Challenge projects - All TDCC domains & NWO	16 Jan 2024	Online	Webinar	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
Q&A Challenge projects - LSH Round 2	13 Mar 2023	Online	Webinar	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
Q&A Challenge projects - LSH Round 2	14 Mar 2023	Online	Webinar	█	█	█	█	█	█	█

Appendix 2b: TDCC-LSH events 2022-2024: detailed information

In this appendix more details are given for a number of the TDCC-LSH events listed in Appendix 2a.

Events:

1. Meetings LSRI teams & TDCC team (Feb 15 and Apr 14 2023)
2. "The DCC Network, Who are we, how do we operate and how do we collaborate with each other?" - LDCCs & TDCCs workshop (Mar 15 2023)
3. "Building capacity for data stewardship in the Netherlands: formal job profiles, training and career perspective" - TDCC-LSH workshop (Apr 4 2023)
4. FAIR trainers workshop (Jun 1 2023)
5. "Addressing bottlenecks together to encourage FAIR practice in research methods, data and software"- TDCCs workshop on Open Science Festival (Aug 31 2023)
6. "Teaming up across domains" - TDCCs & LCRDM event (Feb 27 2024)
7. "Biodiversity & ecology data steward network meeting" - Naturalis, Westerdijk Institute, NIOO, ARISE, LTER-LIFE, SURF, DANS, NLeSC and TDCC-LSH event (May 17 2024)

1. Meeting LSRI teams & TDCC team (15 Feb and Apr 14 2023)

Two dedicated LSRI meetings were held in the Spring of 2023, in which several invited LSRI's (e.g. ARISE, BBMRI-NL, NEMI, NL-Bioimaging-AM, X-Omics, NPEC, UNLOCK, BSL3 Biosafety lab and u-NMR-NL Grid), communities (BioSB, ELIXIR-NL), foundations (GO FAIR Foundation, Health-RI) and funders (ZonMW, NWO) were invited to discuss potential collaborative topics to work on together. All LSRI's presented their scope, their partners and expertise as well as their challenges. A selection of shared challenges and needs that were mentioned are: a) Making data FAIR at the source b) how to convince researchers that it is beneficial to make their data FAIR c) how to make data resources and infrastructures sustainable d) lack of a comprehensive overview of the current landscape (e.g. tools, trainings, FAIR experts, standards). It was concluded that many of the LSRI's share similar data-related challenges, and that there is enthusiasm to work towards collaboratively tackling those challenges. Afterwards, several meetings and conversations have taken place with individual LSRI's. Two concrete follow-up activities consisted of a co-organised workshop in July 2023 with the Green Life Sciences community (NPEC, UNLOCK, ARISE, LTERlife) and a workshop co-organised in May 2024 with the Biodiversity community (ARISE, LTERlife).

Figure 11: Impression photos of the "Collaborate topics among LSRI's" - Large Scale Research Infrastructures & TDCC workshops on the 15th of Feb 2023 & 14th of April 2023

2. "The DCC Network, Who are we, how do we operate and how do we collaborate with each other?" - LDCCs & TDCCs workshop (Mar 15, 2023)

To gain a better understanding of each other’s position in the landscape TDCCs and LDCCs organised a workshop with the topic: “The DCC Network, Who are we?, how do we operate and how do we collaborate with each other?”⁵¹ In the afternoon the TDCCs introduced themselves and provided an update on their latest development plans, upcoming events or projects. Afterwards, several case studies on how to deal with domain specific questions from researchers or data stewards were discussed. This further clarified how to optimally structure a mutual cooperation between the TDCCs and the LDCCs. Overall, the day proved to be incredibly insightful and the enthusiasm and willingness to collaborate with each other truly shined through.

Figure 12: Impression photos of the "The DCC Network, Who are we?, how do we operate and how do we collaborate with each other?" workshop.

⁵¹ <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.7735865>

3. "Building capacity for data stewardship in the Netherlands: formal job profiles, training and career perspective" - TDCC-LSH workshop (Apr 4, 2023)

In April 2023, two years after the publication of the NPOS report on Professionalizing Data Stewardship⁵², 30 representatives from Dutch research organisations met at the Holland Heart House in Utrecht to discuss lessons learnt from the adoption and implementation of official data stewards job profiles in the Netherlands. Policy and decision makers, data steward coordinators and data stewards discussed progress with regards to five recommendations from the report.

All agreed that data stewards are nowadays well organised and easy to find at Dutch RPOs. As to the formalisation of data steward job profiles, universities and some academic hospitals are more advanced than the Universities of Applied Science. More clarity on data stewards' tasks within these organisations would probably help to get the job profiles officially adopted. None of the presenters was satisfied with the current data steward capacity at their institution. To increase this capacity, it was suggested to team up with all stakeholders and find senior researchers or deans who can act as ambassadors for data stewardship. With regards to the availability of education and training of data stewards, there is still work to do. There are well established and popular data management / data stewardship courses in the Netherlands: **Essentials 4 Data Support** (attended by over 500 data professionals since 2013) and the '**DCC spring training days**' (organised since 2021 for and by the data stewards at the local Digital Competence Centers under the umbrella of the **National Coordination Point RDM** (LCRDM)). Participants concluded that a next step would be to set up a nationally certified professional education for data stewards. The table below summarizes the findings of the workshop and a full report⁵³ has also been published, as well as a blog post⁵⁴.

⁵² Professionalising data stewardship in the Netherlands. Competences, training and education. Dutch roadmap towards national implementation of FAIR data stewardship, Mijke Jetten et al. (2021)

<https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.4320504>

⁵³ <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.8026658>

⁵⁴ <https://tdcc.nl/building-capacity-for-data-stewardship-in-the-netherlands-formal-job-profiles-training-and-career-perspective/>

	Recommendation	All	Next steps
1	Formalization of job profile data steward		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create clarity on the data stewardship tasks • Make open science achievements such as open data or software competitive to make the case for investing in data stewardship for (faculty) boards
2	Data stewards are well organized and easy to find		
3	Build data steward capacity		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Team up with all stakeholders in your organization, including HR staff and senior researchers or deans who can act as ambassadors for data stewardship • Find funds for structural and sustainable data stewardship support
4	Ensure the availability of (certified) education and training of data stewards		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Set up acknowledged professional training for data stewards and explore if a professional association is desirable (cf. software engineering societies or privacy officers' associations)
5	Use job profiles for career perspective data stewards		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Make FAIR and data stewardship meaningful by focusing less on compliance and more on societal responsibility • Allow data stewards time to be part of the research team and recognize their efforts as part of the team's work

Figure 13: outcomes of the April 2023 workshop Building capacity for data stewardship in the Netherlands: formal job profiles, training and career perspective

4. FAIR trainers workshop, 1 June 2023, AUMC

We brought together experts in FAIR training across domains and organisations in the Netherlands⁵⁵ to explore how we can boost training in FAIR implementation by setting up a community of FAIR trainers / training developers. Unfortunately, only a small number of those who expressed their interest were able to join us in Amsterdam, but already we had lively discussions, shared experiences and explored ideas on how to organise collaboration. We concluded that an overview of trainers / experts and materials for training on FAIR implementation is currently lacking and that it would be beneficial to have an official structure to foster the materials and develop criteria to assess the quality of training materials (in view of future accreditation). These conclusions led us to submit the LEARN FAIR proposal for the TDCC LSH Challenge call (see below project #7), that was accepted by the TDCC-LSH Programme Board and is currently under review with NWO.

⁵⁵ Representatives from a patient registry (Duchenne); University of Applied Science, UMC; RIVM, Skills4EOSC, Health-RI; ZonMW.

5. "Addressing bottlenecks together to encourage FAIR practice in research methods, data and software"- TDCCs workshop on Open Science Festival (Aug 31, 2023)

On the 31st of August 2023 the 3 thematic DCCs (LSH, SSH and NES) organised a workshop⁵⁶ and had a booth at the Open Science Festival at the Erasmus University in Rotterdam. The goal was to better understand the bottlenecks communities are facing in the uptake of FAIR practices. With a mix of 35 RDM professionals, researchers, and Open Science enthusiasts in the room, we opened the session by positioning the Thematic DCCs within the existing landscape from the perspective of researchers and institutions. Focusing on the TDCC goals to strengthen domain-specific networks and to address digital infrastructure and computational challenges that go beyond individual institutions. Interesting challenges around privacy, arising from handling patient data, but also very unique ones - for example regulations for medical machines/equipment were mentioned in the LSH domain. There seemed to be a strong need to create places and opportunities to bring Data Stewards, Data Managers, Research Software Engineers and researchers together, as they seem to meet like-minded peers in rather different places. It was also discussed to rethink and stop perpetuating the “academic staff” versus. “support staff” split, as it no longer serves the scientific community or reflects current practices. While many of the noted challenges arise from domain specific practices and needs, they were actually shared across all TDCC domains and communities. The received input was particularly useful for updating TDCC roadmaps and determining our future strategic goals and topics.

Figure 14: Impression photos of the "Addressing bottlenecks together to encourage FAIR practice in research methods, data and software" event.

⁵⁶ <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.8338486>

6. "Teaming up across domains" - TDCCs & LCRDM event (Feb 27, 2024)

On 27th of February 2024 the three Thematic DCC Life Sciences & Health (LSH), Social Sciences & Humanities (SSH), Natural & Engineering Sciences (NES) and the National Coordination point of Research Data Management (LCRDM) organized a large event with the theme “Teaming Up Across Domains” in Utrecht. Teaming up with the Research Data Alliance NL (RDA-NL), the Data Steward Interest Group (DSIG), and Local DCCs, the day focused on making progress through collaboration with hands-on sessions and ample networking opportunities. The Life Science and Health track parallel session workshops focused on FAIRification of data in the microbial and rare diseases sub-domains with sessions titled: An introduction in FAIR end-to-end data management⁵⁷ and European Joint Programme on Rare Diseases (EJP RD): teaming up to make FAIR data a reality.⁵⁸. It was a phenomenal event with well over 210 participants, filled with 10 community-led workshops, an inspiring keynote speaker, 6 flash talks demonstrating community initiatives, and a rather informal and welcoming atmosphere. It was truly a community-driven Teaming Up event.

Figure 15: Impression photos of the “Teaming Up Across Domains” event.

7. "Biodiversity & ecology data steward network meeting" - Naturalis, Westerdijk Institute, NIOO, ARISE, LTER-LIFE, SURF, DANS, NLeSC and TDCC-LSH event (May 17, 2024)

On the 17th of May 2024, Naturalis, Westerdijk Institute, NIOO, ARISE, LTER-LIFE, SURF, DANS, NLeSC and TDCC-LSH organised a workshop that focused harmonising best practices, exploring specific biodiversity and ecology requirements data stewards might have with respect to data or e-science competence and to address common challenges faced in the Biodiversity & ecology data space. Several collaborative research institutions, large scale research infrastructures, communities and

⁵⁷ Organised by Peter Schaap and Jasper Koehorst, WUR

⁵⁸ Organised by Joeri van der Velde, UMCG

technical e-infrastructure providers came together to discuss a biodiversity & ecology platform which encompasses a data stewards network that has links to national and international initiatives regarding the technical and social aspects of biodiversity and ecological data stewardship and e-science. There was great enthusiasm from the Biodiversity & ecology communities to collaborate and to further harmonise best practices. The output of the workshop was used to optimise a drafted proposal of the Biodiversity & ecology community that was submitted to the TDCC-LSH challenge project call.

Figure 16: Impression photo of the "Biodiversity & ecology data steward network meeting " workshop.

Appendix 3a: The TDCC-LSH Challenge project process

The TDCC-LSH conducted two project rounds in 2023-2024, each with their own project deadlines: indicated as (Round 1 / Round 2). For more information about the process itself, please refer to the guideline below, which is also summarized in the figure and table below) and which can also be found on the TDCC-LSH website.⁵⁹

To bring the Challenge project call to the attention of the community the TDCC-LSH organized several Q & A meetings on the project call for the life sciences and health communities (Slides and FAQ documents⁶⁰):

- 19 December 2023 15.00 - 16.00 (TDCC-LSH round 1)
- 20 December 2023 15.00 - 16.00 (TDCC-LSH round 1)
- 16 January 2024 13.00 - 14.30 All TDCC domains & NWO
- 13 March 2024 13:00 - 14:00 (TDCC-LSH round 2)
- 14 March 2024 10:00 - 11:00 (TDCC-LSH round 2)

TDCC-LSH Challenge project process

Figure 17: The TDCC-LSH challenge project process

⁵⁹ <https://tdcc.nl/nwo-tdcc-call-2023/tdcc-lsh-project-development-process/>

⁶⁰ <https://tdcc.nl/nwo-tdcc-call-2023/tdcc-lsh-project-development-process/>

Step 1. Submit your idea to the TDCC-LSH using the Expression of Interest form

Deadline(s): Round 1: 08 Jan 2024 / Round 2: 05 Apr 2024

On the 15th of November 2023 the NWO TDCC call will open, and the Expression of Interest form will be available on the TDCC website. Applicants can submit their idea by filling in the Expression of interest form. Here you will be asked to write a short description about your project ideas, collaborating partners and which TDCC-LSH roadmap challenges your project addresses.

*Please note that while the NWO call remains open till the 15th of November 2024, the deadlines for obtaining a TDCC submission letter will be closing sooner due to the review process involved! Hence, make sure to submit an idea before the deadline and the Expression of Interest form closes.

[Expression of interest submission form](#)

Step 1,5: TDCC-LSH team will be contacting and connecting initiatives

Applicants can expect a response: Round 1: 15 Jan 2024 / Round 2: 26 Apr 2024

After submission the TDCC-LSH will do a limited criteria check (domain relevance, addressing roadmap challenges, collaboration potential, etc.), to see if the submitted Expression of Interest idea is potentially eligible for a TDCC-LSH submission letter. The TDCC-LSH team will then compare all applications and if relevant match them with other submitted ideas or already existing projects and initiatives in the TDCC-LSH community. The TDCC-LSH team will then contact and connect applicants as needed and can also facilitate project meetings with the aim of fostering or strengthening collaboration between initiatives.

Step 2: Refine idea and write a pre-proposal

Deadline(s): Round 1: 19 Feb 2024 / Round 2: 07 Jun 2024

After an initial meeting for all successful participants (date to be confirmed), all the teams will be asked to translate their expression of interest ideas into a more comprehensive project plan. Project teams will conduct their own process to align ideas and make sure that the submitted project is in line with the community needs, resulting in a pre-proposal that combines ideas and connects different initiatives. Finally, the project teams will be asked to submit their pre-proposal before the deadline indicated above to the TDCC-LSH team. The TDCC-LSH team will then send the pre-proposals to the TDCC-LSH Programme Board for review.

[Pre-Proposal Template](#)

Step 2,5: TDCC-LSH Programme Board review decision and feedback

Applicants can expect a response: Round 1: 18 Mar 2024 / Round 2: 05 Jul 2024

The TDCC-LSH Programme Board will evaluate the application, suggest other potential partners and provide overall feedback on the proposal. Applicants will receive confirmation that the proposals will either be: rejected, revisited at a later stage or be approved and thus allowing applicants to proceed to step 3, writing the full proposal.

Step 3: Writing and submitting the full proposal

Deadline(s): Round 1: 01 May 2024 / Round 2: 27 Sep 2024

Once writing teams have obtained the approval of the TDCC-LSH Programme Board they will write the full proposal. The full project proposal needs to be written following the format of the application form provided by NWO, available in ISAAC.

*More information about the forms, the TDCC call, or ISAAC can be found on the NWO website.

[TDCC NWO Call, Application form and Budget form](#)

Step 3,5: Final check and decision by TDCC-LSH programme board

Applicants can expect a response: Round 1: 15 May 2024 /Round 2: 11 Oct 2024

The TDCC-LSH programme board will review the final proposals. Applicants will receive confirmation that the proposals will either be: rejected, revisited at a later stage or be approved and thus allowing applicants to proceed to step 4 & 5, submitting the full proposal.

Step 4. Obtain letter of Submission by TDCC-LSH

Applicants can expect a response: Round 1: 03 Jun 2024 / Round 2: 25 Oct 2024

Once the project proposal has received positive feedback from the TDCC-LSH programme board, the applicant(s) will receive the letter of submission by email of TDCC-LSH that is needed to complete the NWO call.

Step 5. Applicants submit the proposal to NWO through ISAAC

Deadline(s): 15 Jun 2024 13 Jun 2024 * per request of NWO / 15 Nov 2024 (14 Nov 2024* per request of NWO due to limited ISAAC support on the 15th)

After obtaining the letter of submission from the TDCC-LSH, the applicant can submit their proposal to the NWO call through ISAAC.

Appendix 3b: Overview TDCC-LSH projects

In this appendix overviews are given from:

1. Project proposals 2023-2024, including keywords as filled in by the applicants
2. Word cloud based on the TDCC-LSH challenge project proposals 2023-2024
3. Overview of organisations/institutes involved in all project proposals
4. Detailed information about the 3 challenge projects and the fellowship project that are currently under review with NWO

1. Project proposals 2023-2024, including keywords as filled in by the applicants

Nr	Title	Keywords						
1	genAI for training & support in digital LSH research	only EoI - no (pre-proposal)						
2	Scaling BASELINE implementation across DCCs	ELSI	GDPR	Data Protection	Informed consent			
3	Patient Centered Anticoagulation Data Research	H7 FHIR R4	Personal Health Train	openEHR	General practitioner	Thrombosis		
4	FAIR Expert Team	FAIR Data Stewardship	FAIR Data	Capacity Building	Interoperability			
5	ABCDE: Aligned Biodiversity Community on Data & eScience	biodiversity	ecology	FAIR	community of practice	capacity building	foundational infrastructure	data interoperability
6	A FAIR tool framework for bioinformatics services, tools and workflows in digital Life Sciences and Health (LSH) research	Tools and software,	FAIR	research data management	communities	training		
7	LEARN-FAIR: Life Science & Health Educational Alignment for Research and Networking in FAIR Data Management	FAIR Data Stewardship	community building	open educational resources				
8	Cohort and mentorship training in open skills for the LSH domain	only EoI - no (pre-proposal)						
9	FAIRworkflow2K - 1000 students and 1000 researchers empowered by FAIR workflows to tackle digital challenges	FAIR workflows	Galaxy	Nextflow	Sustainability	Education	use cases	
10	Training the next generation of FAIR-aware and AI-savvy data scientists for the LSH domain	Education	Data Stewardship	FAIR workflows	Artificial Intelligence	bioinformatics and systems biology		

11	Federated Learning for Privacy-Preserving Microscopy Image Analysis	Federated Learning	Microscopy	Image analysis	community	infrastructure		
12	Multimodal Monitoring of the Respiratory System: an integrated analysis platform (M3Resp)	standardized analysis & metadata	time-series data	community-driven development	FAIR software	respiratory monitoring		
13	Towards a smoother research journey with Interoperable Data Management Plans (iDMPs)	Data Management Plan	Interoperability	FAIR	harmonization	research journey		
14	CastorDataBridge: A community-driven Python library designed to facilitate programmatic interaction with Castor EDC	Open Source	community driven	FAIR	reproducibility	research software engineering		
15	FAME: FAIR Metadata Exchange: Enhancing interoperability across research infrastructures	infrastructure	cross-platform	accessibility	FAIR	metadata		
16	Health-MetaSyn: FAIR and safe synthetic data from health record meta-data	synthetic data	privacy sensitive	federated analysis	software tool	metadata		
17	Strengthening the Impact of Health Research by connecting Patient-driven Infrastructures for Citizen Generated Data	citizen science	citizen generated data	patient fora and platforms	experience stories	research tools		
18	Global Initiative for Multi-Modal AI Benchmarking in Medical Imaging and Omics: Leveraging the Grand Challenge Platform	benchmarking	omics	imaging	multi-modal AI			
19	Prospective harmonization of variables through Common Data Elements – Towards a core dataset for cohort studies in the Netherlands	prospective harmonization	common data elements	longitudinal cohort study	core data set			
20	Brain and neurocognitive development in sickle cell disease (BRICK-study)	only EoI - no (pre-proposal)						
21	FAIRify your metabolomics data: achieving convergence on standards for reuse-ready data and workflows (FAIRify)	metabolomics	FAIR data	FAIR workflows	Data Stewardship practices	Data Stewardship Training		
22	TREAT: veTeRinary patiEnt dATa	veterinary medicine	animal welfare	animal patient data				

3. Overview of organisations/institutes involved in all project proposals

The table below shows the distribution of affiliations of the applicants for the TDCC-LSH challenge projects. (Note: in green the 3 projects are highlighted that are currently submitted to NWO and in red the proposals that did not move further than the EoI phase).

Overview of Lead- and Co-applicant affiliations in pre-proposals

Name	Abbreviation	Location	Project number																						Total
			1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	
University Medical Centers (UMC)																									
Amsterdam UMC	AMC & VUmc	Amsterdam																							9
University Medical Center Rotterdam	Erasmus MC	Rotterdam																							7
Radboud University Medical Center	Radboudumc	Nijmegen																							5
University Medical Center Utrecht	UMCU	Utrecht																							5
University Medical Center Groningen	UMCG	Groningen																							5
Leiden University Medical Center	LUMC	Leiden																							7
Maastricht University Medical Centre+	MUMC+	Maastricht																							2
Universities																									
Erasmus University	EUR	Rotterdam																							0
Radboud University	RU	Nijmegen																							0
Tilburg University	TiU	Tilburg																							0
University of Groningen	RUG	Groningen																							2
Delft University of Technology	TUD	Delft																							2
Eindhoven University of Technology	TU/e	Eindhoven																							1
University of Twente	UT	Enschede																							1
Maastricht University	UM	Maastricht																							5
Leiden University	LU	Leiden																							3
Utrecht University	UU	Utrecht																							3
University of Amsterdam	Uva	Amsterdam																							2
Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam	VU	Amsterdam																							4
Wageningen University & Research	WUR	Wageningen																							7
Open Universiteit	OU	Heerlen																							0
Large Scale Research Infrastructures (LSRI) & National Growth Fund (NGF)																									
Health-RI		National																							7
ARISE		National																							1
LTER-LIFE		National																							1
NL-Bioimaging		National																							2
NEMI		National																							1
UNLOCK		National																							1
hDMT INFRA StemCells		National																							1
X-Omics		National																							1
E-infrastructures																									
SURF	SURF	Utrecht																							3
eScience Center NL	NLeSC	Amsterdam																							5
Data Archiving and Networked Services	DANS	Den Haag																							1
Industry																									
anDREa B.V. (Digital Research Environment)	AnDREa	Nijmegen																							1
FAIR solutions B.V.	FAIR solutions	Waddinxveen																							1
The Hyve B.V.	The Hyve	Utrecht																							1
dsm-firmenich	dsm-firmenich																								1
Other																									
ELIXIR Netherlands	ELIXIR-NL	(Inter)National																							2
Naturalis	NBC	Leiden																							2
Netherlands Institute of Ecology	NIOO-KNAW	Wageningen																							1
Westerdijk Fungal Biodiversity Institute	WI-KNAW	Utrecht																							1
Prinses Máxima Centrum	PMC	Utrecht																							1
Avans Hogeschool	Avans	Noord-Brabant																							1
Netherlands Organisation for Applied Scientific Research	TNO	National																							1
Go FAIR Foundation	GFF	Leiden																							1
Exposome Netherlands	Exposome-NL	National																							1
Total			2	2	2	5	8	12	5	2	7	4	4	4	3	3	8	2	1	5	7	3	18	2	

4. Overview of submitted TDCC-LSH projects (September 2024)

TDCC-LSH project reference ID: TDCC-LSH Bottleneck project #1

Title: Strengthening the Dutch LSH FAIR data stewardship landscape – installing a national cohort of FAIR LSH fellows

Key words: Fellowship, LSRI, domain specific data stewards, national network of experts, training, FAIR implementation

Project lead: Dr. C.W.G. (Celia) van Gelder

Duration: 18 months

Budget: € 877.776

Responsible institution(s) and department(s):

- Wageningen University & Research (WUR), Systems and Synthetic Biology & UNLOCK
- Wageningen University & Research (WUR), Genetics & NPEC
- Naturalis, ARISE
- Leiden University (LU), LIACS & NEMI & NL-Bioimaging
- UMC Groningen (UMCG), Faculty of Medical Sciences & NEMI & NL-Bioimaging
- UMC Groningen (UMCG), Genetics, Genomics Coordination Center & X-Omics
- Amsterdam UMC (AUMC), Medical Informatics
- GO FAIR Foundation (GFF)
- Health-RI

Public Summary:

Digital research data is increasingly important for research in the life sciences and the health domain. This programme aims to increase the knowledge needed to carefully manage this data and, if possible, make it usable for follow-up research. Research institutions in the Netherlands can delegate a fellow. The TDCC-LSH fellows receive training and work for a year under the guidance of a coach on their digital skills and on joint solutions. This creates a national network of experts that ensures that knowledge is shared and can be applied by all research organizations in this domain.

TDCC-LSH project reference ID: TDCC-LSH Challenge project #6

Project Status: Approved by TDCC-LSH Programme board & NWO

Title: A FAIR tool framework for bioinformatics services, tools and workflows in digital Life Sciences and Health (LSH) research

Key words: Tools and software, FAIR, research data management, communities, training

Project lead: Dr. H. (Halima) Mouhib

Duration: 24 months

Budget: € 394.325

Responsible institution(s) and department(s):

- Maastricht University (UM), Department of Bioinformatics - BiGCaT
- Prinses Máxima Centrum voor Kinderoncologie (PMC), Research Department
- Leiden University Medical Centre (LUMC), Department of Human Genetics
- Leiden University Medical Centre (LUMC), Center for Proteomics and Metabolomics
- University Medical Center Groningen (UMCG), Department of Genetics
- Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam (VU), Department of Computer Science
- Amsterdam UMC (AUMC), Department of Research Data Management
- Netherlands eScience Center (NLeSC)
- SURF, Research Development
- Health-RI
- Wageningen University & Research (WUR), Bioinformatics Department
- Radboudumc, Department of Medical BioSciences

Public Summary:

Various tools and services are available for Life Science and Health data research, but users cannot easily find them or assess their quality. As a result, they are not used, or even similar tools are redeveloped. Together with developers, experts and users, we develop a toolkit for finding suitable tools and services. This is applied to existing tools and those under development and can be used with new tools in the future. With examples, training, interactive work sessions and collaboration with established platforms and communities, tools and services become sustainably accessible to end users and (further) development cycles for developers.

TDCC-LSH project reference ID: TDCC-LSH Challenge project #7

Project Status: Approved by TDCC-LSH Programme board & NWO

Title: LEARN-FAIR: Life Science & Health Educational Alignment for Research and Networking in FAIR Data Management

Key words: FAIR Data Stewardship, Community Building, Open Educational Resources

Project lead: Dr. M.G. (Martijn) Kersloot

Duration: 24 months

Budget: € 399.857

Responsible institution(s) and department(s):

- Amsterdam UMC (AUMC), Medical Informatics
- Health-RI
- Leiden University Medical Centre (LUMC), Department of Human Genetics
- Maastricht University (UM), DataHub
- Radboud UMC (RUMC), Department of Medical BioSciences

Public Summary:

The LEARN-FAIR project intends to foster cooperation and knowledge exchange among FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable data) trainers by establishing a Dutch FAIR Trainers Community. Additionally, the project focuses on identifying training needs for researchers and data stewards, as well as existing educational materials, in order to develop new Open Educational Resources. To ensure that these materials meet the (future) needs of the community, the LEARN-FAIR project combines empirical research with active community engagement.

TDCC-LSH project reference ID: TDCC-LSH Challenge project #10

Project Status: Approved by TDCC-LSH Programme board & NWO

Title: Training the next generation of FAIR-aware and AI-savvy data scientists for the LSH domain

Key words: Education, data stewardship, FAIR workflows, artificial intelligence, bioinformatics and systems biology

Project lead: Dr. ir. P. (Perry) Moerland

Duration: 24 months

Budget: € 243.158

Responsible institution(s) and department(s):

- Amsterdam UMC (AUMC), Epidemiology and Data Science
- Wageningen University & Research (WUR), Bioinformatics
- Eindhoven University of Technology (TU/e), Biomedical engineering
- Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam (VU), Computer science
- Wageningen University & Research (WUR), Systems and Synthetic Biology

Public Summary:

For professionals in life sciences and health (LSH), it's increasingly crucial to (i) efficiently link findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR) data with computational workflows that process the data (FAIR workflows); (ii) ensure that the data produced by FAIR workflows can be seamlessly utilized for artificial intelligence (AI) applications (AI-ready); (iii) construct AI models while integrating pertinent domain-specific knowledge (AI-savvy). The objective of this project is to create two new post-Master's courses on FAIR workflows and advanced machine learning/modern AI technology for life sciences. These courses aim to address the existing gap in equipping researchers with these essential skills.

